

COMPTON EFFECT

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Compton Effect: Further confirmation of the particle model of e. m. radiation.

- ❖ *Compton Effect was discovered by Arthur Holly Compton in 1923 and for this discovery he was awarded by the Nobel Prize in Physics in 1927.*
- ❖ *According to classical theory of scattering, the wavelength of X-ray would not be changing (**Thomson scattering**) after interaction with the electrons, however Compton did find a change in wavelength in experiment. Then Compton Effect was explained on the basis of the quantum theory (particle “photon” model) of light.*
- ❖ *This Effect convinced remaining doubters of the existence of photons. It constitutes very strong evidence in support of the **Quantum Theory** of radiation.*

Definitions:

When a scattering of a **high energy photon** by a free charged particle (usually a loosely bound outer-shell electron in target material) results an increase in wavelength between scattered and initial photon, then it is called Compton Effect. It is also known as **Compton Scattering**.

The Compton Effect is an **incoherent and inelastic scattering** of a photon by an **elastic collision** with electron in which both **relativistic energy and momentum** are conserved. Here both photon and electron treated as **relativistic particles**.

Compton Effect results in both **attenuation** and also **absorption** of radiation.

The difference between wavelengths of initial photon and scattered photon is known as **Compton Shift**.

Experimental demonstration of the Compton Effect

Figure 2.22 (a) The scattering of a photon by an electron is called the Compton effect. Energy and momentum are conserved in such an event, and as a result the scattered photon has less energy (longer wavelength) than the incident photon. (b) Vector diagram of the momenta and their components of the incident and scattered photons and the scattered electron.

Mathematical description of Compton Effect

The above figures 2 represents collision two particle: an x-ray photon (zero rest mass) and an electron (rest mass m and initially at rest). After this striking the scattered away with an angle ϕ from its original direction while the electron receives an impulse and begins to move with a speed v by making an angle θ with direction of incident photon . It is consider that the photon transfer some energy to the electron. Due to energy loss, the frequency of the incident photon ν changes to a lower value ν' .

Loss in photon energy = Kinetic Energy (KE) gain by **recoil electron**

$$h\nu - h\nu' = \text{KE} \quad [\text{h is planck constant}]$$

Momentum of a massless particle (here 'photon') is given by Theory of Relativity as:

photon momentum = $(h\nu)/c$ [c is speed of light in vacuum and ν is frequency of photon]

Momentum is a vector quantity so in this **two-body** collision momentum must be conserved in each of two mutually perpendicular directions. Now momentum of incident photon is $h\nu/c$ and scattered photon is $h\nu'/c$

c. The initial and final momentum of electron is $\mathbf{0}$ and \mathbf{p} .

Along direction of incident photon, the conservation of momentum gives:

Total initial momentum = Total final momentum

$$\frac{h\nu}{c} + \mathbf{0} = \frac{h\nu'}{c} \cos\phi + \mathbf{p} \cos\theta \quad \dots\dots (1)$$

Along perpendicular to the direction of incident photon, the conservation of momentum gives:

$$\mathbf{0} = \frac{h\nu'}{c} \sin\phi - \mathbf{p} \sin\theta \quad \dots\dots (2)$$

Multiply equations 1 and 2 by c we get:

$$\mathbf{pc} \cos\theta = h\nu - h\nu' \cos\phi \quad \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

$$\mathbf{pc} \sin\theta = h\nu' \sin\phi \quad \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

By squaring eqn. 3 and 4 and then adding them we get:

$$\mathbf{p^2 c^2} = (h\nu)^2 - 2(h\nu)(h\nu') \cos\phi + (h\nu')^2 \quad \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

From the Theory of Relativity, the total energy of **recoil electron** is given by the equations:

Total Energy = KE + Rest Mass Energy

$$\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{KE} + \mathbf{mc^2} \quad \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

$$\mathbf{E^2} = \mathbf{m^2 c^4} + \mathbf{p^2 c^2} \quad \dots\dots\dots (7)$$

From equation 6 and 7 it can be written that,

$$\mathbf{(KE + mc^2)^2} = \mathbf{m^2 c^4} + \mathbf{p^2 c^2}$$

$$\mathbf{(KE)^2} + \mathbf{2 mc^2 KE} = \mathbf{p^2 c^2} \quad \dots\dots\dots (8)$$

Now, substituting the value $\mathbf{KE} = (h\nu - h\nu')$ in equation 8 we get

$$\mathbf{p^2 c^2} = (h\nu)^2 - 2(h\nu)(h\nu') + (h\nu')^2 + 2 mc^2 (h\nu - h\nu') \quad \dots\dots\dots (9)$$

Substituting the value of $\mathbf{p^2 c^2}$ from equation 5 into 9 we finally obtain

$$\mathbf{2 mc^2 (h\nu - h\nu')} = \mathbf{2 (h\nu)(h\nu') (1 - \cos\phi)} \quad \dots\dots\dots (10)$$

Dividing the eq. 10 by $(2h^2 c^2)$ we obtain

$$\frac{mc}{h} \left(\frac{\nu}{c} - \frac{\nu'}{c} \right) = \frac{\nu}{c} \frac{\nu'}{c} (1 - \cos\phi) \quad \dots\dots (10)$$

Now from definition of wavelength we have: $\frac{\nu}{c} = \frac{1}{\lambda}$ and $\frac{\nu'}{c} = \frac{1}{\lambda'}$ and then eq. 10 becomes

$$\frac{mc}{h} \left(\frac{1}{\lambda} - \frac{1}{\lambda'} \right) = \frac{1 - \cos \phi}{\lambda \lambda'}$$

$$\lambda - \lambda' = \frac{h}{mc} (1 - \cos \phi)$$

$$\Delta\lambda = \lambda_c (1 - \cos \phi) \dots\dots\dots (12)$$

This eq. **12** was derived By A. H. Compton and it describes the phenomenon known as Compton Effect. The term $\Delta\lambda$ gives the change in photon wavelength due Scattering with a free electron and it is called **Compton Shift**.

- From eq. 12 it is clear that the **Compton Shift is independent of the wavelength of the incident photon and depend on scattering angle**.
- The term $\lambda_c = \frac{h}{mc}$ is called **Compton Wavelength** of the **scattering particle (Here electron)**.
- For an electron $\lambda_c = 2.426 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m} = 2.426 \text{ pm}$ ($10^{-12} \text{ m} = 1 \text{ pm}$)
- Eq. **12** gives that Compton Shift becomes **maximum** for $\phi = 180^\circ$ and then

$$\Delta\lambda_{\text{max}} = 2\lambda_c$$

The maximum change in wavelength is (for scattering from an electron)
 $= 4.86 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m}$

This value would be **insignificant for visible light** ($\lambda \sim 10^{-7} \text{ m}$) but this wavelength shift is **significant for x-ray** ($\lambda \sim 10^{-10} \text{ m}$).

$$\text{Compton wavelength} \equiv \lambda_c = \frac{h}{mc}$$

$$\text{rewriting: } mc = h \frac{1}{\lambda_c} \Rightarrow mc^2 = hc \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_c} \right) = hf$$

What is smallest wavelength possible for an EM wave?

Photons with a wavelength **smaller** than λ_c tend to split into electron-positron pairs.

The Compton Shift is depends on scattering angle:

This figures show the experimental confirmation of Compton Effect. The greater the scattering angle, the greater the wavelength shift.

Comparison of Compton Effect with other interaction process between radiation and Matter:

The three main ways of interaction between radiation and matter are:

- Compton effect
- Photoelectric Effect
- Pair Production

Figure 2.27 X- and gamma rays interact with matter chiefly through the photoelectric effect, Compton scattering, and pair production. Pair production requires a photon energy of at least 1.02 MeV.

The relative probability of occurrence of Compton Scattering over other processes depends on the **energy of radiation** and **atomic number of the target elements**.

- In lighter elements (Ex. Carbon), Compton Effect becomes dominant for a few tens of keV energy of radiation (photon).
- For heavier element (Ex. Lead) Compton scattering does not occur until photon energies becomes ~ 1 Mev.

Application of Compton Effect:

- Used in astronomy.
- Used in radiotherapy and nuclear medicine.
- In material physics.

Reference:

1. A. Beiser, "Concept of Modern Physics" (Tata McGraw- Hill Edition)
2. R. Eisberg and R. Resnick, "Quantum Physics of Atoms, Molecules, Solids, Nuclei, and Particles" (Wiley India Edition)
3. Google Image

Numerical Problem: From

Q.1) X-rays of wavelength 10.0 pm are scattered from a target. (a) Find the wavelength of x-rays scattered through 45° . (b) Find the maximum wavelength present in the scattered x-rays. (c) Find the maximum kinetic energy of the recoil electrons.

Solution: (a) From the expression of Compton shift we can write: $\Delta\lambda = \lambda_c (1 - \cos \phi)$ where, λ and λ' are wavelengths of incident and scattered x-ray respectively and ϕ is scattering angle.

λ_c = Compton wavelength of recoil electron = 2.426 pm and given that, $\phi = 45^\circ$; $\lambda = 10.0$ pm

$$\lambda' = \lambda + \lambda_c (1 - \cos \phi) = [10.0 + 2.426 (1 - \cos 45^\circ)] \text{ pm} = [10.0 + 2.426 (1 - 0.707)] \text{ pm}$$

$$\lambda' = [10.0 + (2.426 \times 0.293)] \text{ pm} = 10.71 \text{ pm}$$

(b) Maximum wavelength of scattered x-ray = $\lambda'_{\max} = \lambda + \Delta\lambda_{\max} = \lambda + 2\lambda_c = [10.0 + (2 \times 2.426)] \text{ pm} = 14.9 \text{ pm}$

(c) From the of kinetic energy of recoil electron $\text{KE} = hc \left(\frac{1}{\lambda} - \frac{1}{\lambda'} \right)$ it clear that KE is becomes maximum for maximum λ' . Here h is Planck constant and c is speed of light in vacuum. From (b) we have $\lambda'_{\max} = 14.9 \text{ pm}$

$$\text{Therefore, } \text{KE}_{\max} = (6.62 \times 10^{-34}) \text{ J-s } (3 \times 10^8) \text{ ms}^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{10 \text{ pm}} - \frac{1}{14.9 \text{ pm}} \right]$$

$$\text{KE}_{\max} = (6.62 \times 10^{-34}) \text{ J-s } (3 \times 10^8) \text{ ms}^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{10 \text{ m}} - \frac{1}{14.9 \text{ m}} \right] \times 10^{12} = 6.54 \times 10^{-15} \text{ Joule} = 40.8 \text{ keV}$$

$$[1 \text{ Joule} = 1.6 \times 10^{-19} \text{ eV}]$$

Q. 2) At what scattering angle will incident 100 keV x-rays leave a target with an energy of 90 keV.

Solution: The energy of incident x-ray $E = 100 \text{ keV} = 1.6 \times 10^{-14} \text{ Joule}$ and that of scattered x-ray

$E' = 90 \text{ keV} = 1.44 \times 10^{-14} \text{ Joule}$. Let us consider that the scattering angle = ϕ

Wavelength of incident x-ray $\lambda = \frac{hc}{E}$, here h is Planck constant and c is speed of light in vacuum.

$$\lambda = [(6.626 \times 10^{-34} \text{ J-s}) (3 \times 10^8 \text{ m})] / (1.6 \times 10^{-14}) \text{ J} = 12.42 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m} = \mathbf{12.42 \text{ pm}} \quad [10^{-12} \text{ m} = 1 \text{ pm}]$$

$$\text{Similarly, wavelength of incident x-ray } \lambda' = [(6.626 \times 10^{-34} \text{ J-s}) (3 \times 10^8 \text{ m})] / (1.44 \times 10^{-14}) \text{ J} = \mathbf{13.8 \text{ pm}}$$

From the expression of Compton shift we can write: $\Delta\lambda = \lambda_c (1 - \cos \phi)$

λ_c = Compton wavelength of recoil electron = 2.426 pm

$$\text{Here } \Delta\lambda = (\lambda' - \lambda) = (13.8 - 12.42) \text{ pm} = 1.38 \text{ pm}$$

$$(1 - \cos \phi) = \Delta\lambda / \lambda_c = (1.38 \text{ pm} / 2.426 \text{ pm}) = 0.56$$

$$\cos \phi = (1 - 0.5688) = 0.4311 = \cos 64^\circ$$

$$\mathbf{\phi = 64^\circ}$$